

Special Issue
Experience of Teaching-Learning & Assessment
In Covid 19 Crisis

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Reflection of Teaching-Learning & Assessment during covid19

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With salvos of Webinars and online teaching during the Covid-19 lockdown, I, as a medical teacher, experienced it from both sides of a table, as a student and as a teacher. However, I thought it more pertinent to reflect here as a student rather than a teacher. The reflection below portrays the feelings of a student during his sojourn of online learning and his intense desire to attend classes. The metaphor is constructed on the premises of an informal feedback from students and reflects how initial enthusiasm melted into complacency, self-disdain, boredom and longing for campus life during extended lockdown.

‘Locked’, but not ‘down’: A student reflects

I got admission in medical college after qualifying NEET examination with decent grades. I could realize the difference between a college and school and soon got acclimatized to distinct routine of long study hours and less sleep. After a few days of feeling of *jamaais vu*, medical college meant much more than a space to learn in class and in campus. I could express myself to the fullest extent. It became my second home. I confirmed to my identity as a learner of modern medicine, who interacted with fellow colleagues and seniors. All was going very well, including my formative assignments, when scourge of Covid-19 pandemic ravaged the mankind across globe. Everyone was scared of human touch, distrusting an essential human bond! As a consequence, the shops and malls were shut, roads closed, trains cancelled, hostels vacated, and classes were suspended *sine die*. All of a sudden I became a *4-wall-home* bound Homo Sapiens Hominis! The familiarity of a routine had made me disciplined and Covid-19 stole away that campus routine from me! Our Dean sir rightly arranged regular online classes.

Initially, I was enthusiastic and enjoyed this mode of learning. However, the sudden shift to home bound online learning with continuous screen gaze, moving objects without expressions, absence of body language, which was hall mark of a typical Physiology or Medicine professor, and discordance between voice and visuals rendered many sessions lackadaisical without enthusiasm and interest. This disinterest culminated into frustration and fatigue as time passed. I felt disconnected from world! Look at the truancy of electrons, a flurry of them made teacher’s face appear clear and smiling, and suddenly its folly blurred his figure into an in-comprehensible haze with incongruence of sound and lights and staccato speech. Often, a teacher appeared as a tiny head making Brownian movements on kaleidoscopic listless screen. Can these visuals be equated to live intellectual performance? Time schedules were disturbed and continuous home stay blurred the boundaries between practicals and theory classes, all falling into one cognitive domain! It is not that I am alone to bear the brunt. Many of my classmates are passing through the same phase.

Earlier, when I visited home with aplomb, I was greeted with awe and appreciation as a budding medic! This gradually vanished and I felt that my identity as medical student was being washed away at home. Parents, brothers and sisters considered me equal to them and expected to share their work and household chores, which I ruefully did. About clothes and attire, less said is better. I felt the pain of caged bird unable to stretch wings and who had forgot the joy of flying. I craved for freedom, companionship and often exhibited bouts of erratic behaviour hitherto uncharacteristic of my composure. Perhaps, I was manifesting 2nd of the 5 stages of Kubler-Ross psychological reactions (Denial, Anger, Bargain, Depression and Acceptance) to extraordinary adversity such as Corona carnage! In bargain, I resolved to cope with this queer situation by getting involved in pursuing my hobbies. I composed allegory, rhymes, imagery, alliteration, and music. I was delighted. I was also advised to practise yoga and meditation to calm nerves and beat burnout of continuous exposure to technology. Who would teach yoga in Corona times except online resources! These practices did help me for quite some time. I, then, made mandatory time off from screen. This actually helped me a lot comforting my eyes.

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Some of my friends felt that everything was changed; food habits, sleeping patterns and study routines. They missed calm and quiet hours of library reading rooms. Others resorted to painting, gardening, extending a helping hand to needy, disseminating importance of social distancing, face mask, and hand washing. Some have done training courses in ventilator use and calligraphy. These vocations motivated me as well.

Hey Corona, you have snatched my free space, identity and confined me within four walls in front of maze of LCDs, a desolated bleak and barren moor, where I am stranded bereft of life. Smiles and pantomimes are replaced by smileys and phantom tales. I miss stroll to café for cookies, a pat on the back, gossips and spirited brainstorming on *much ado about nothings* with friends! I want to go back to the hallowed precincts of my institute.

Meanwhile, academics prevailed upon me in the form of incessant online sessions and assignments on Google forms which I had to comply with. As the lockdown extended further the next salvos came in the form of online viva tests as if I was bubbling with knowledge sans books! Perhaps, the next onslaught would be online sessions on skill acquisition. I shall learn swimming without a dive into river!

PS: Nevertheless, believing in resilience of a human mind to cope up with adversities, I also feel that it is a blessing in disguise and opportunity to identify self. I am convinced that even when Corona crisis is over the technology shall stay and I have to align my learning needs with online resource allocations to make myself future ready tech savvy medic. The pivotal role of medical profession in this situation clearly defines the manner in which we too should commit ourselves to save human race. It is the indeed a need of the hour!

I conclude here with a famous couplet:

माना कि अंधेरा घना है,
मगर दिया जलाना कहाँ मना है!